

Exploring validated HPTLC method of Rivaroxaban in tablet dosage form

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Abstract : Rivaroxaban (Rb) is a FDA approved, orally active anticoagulant drug. A HPTLC method for analysis of Rb in a tablet formulation has been developed and validated. Separation is performed on silica gel 60 F₂₅₄ with toluene-ethyl acetate-methanol, 2 : 1 : 1 (v/v/v) as mobile phase. Densitometric evaluation of the separated zone is carried out at 284 nm. There is no chromatographic interference from the tablet excipients and compact spots are observed for Rb ($R_f = 0.53 \pm 0.02$). Regression analysis of the calibration plot revealed good linearity over the concentration range of 0.5–5 μg . The method is validated for linearity, precision, robustness and recovery in accordance with ICH guidelines. The LOD and LOQ are found to be 0.15 and 0.45 $\mu\text{g}/\text{spot}$ respectively. Stability is checked under acid and alkali hydrolysis. The degradation products are well-resolved from the pure drug and had significantly different R_f values. The developed method might be useful in quality control of Rb in pharmaceutical industry.

Keywords : Rivaroxaban, high performance thin layer chromatography (HPTLC), tablet dosage form.

Introduction

The application of thin layer chromatography (TLC) is increasing in the assays of active ingredient(s) in pharmaceutical formulations¹. TLC is a versatile, inexpensive and effective method that has been adopted in pharmacopoeia as a general quantitative method for use in different stages of pharmaceutical research². More than 90% of separations are performed over silica³.

Rivaroxaban (Rb), a newly FDA approved drug is used to prevent thromboembolic diseases⁴. It is orally active and the mechanism involved for termination of coagulation cascade is the direct inhibition of Factor Xa⁵.

A HPLC followed by tandem mass spectrometry (HPLC-MS/MS) is only reported analytical method for prediction of Rb concentration in plasma during therapeutic drug monitoring⁶. In the present study, an attempt has been made to develop a specific, precise, robust and accurate assay method of Rb in tablet dosage form using TLC followed by densitometric scanning to assess batch to batch content uniformity.

Results and discussion

Isolation and identification of Rb :

Rb is isolated from commercial tablets (Xarelto®, Bayer

Schering Pharma, Germany) and purity is assessed by spectroscopic studies (Fig. 1). The average melting point is found to be 229 °C. The empirical formula of Rb is C₁₉H₁₈ClN₃O₅S. The ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 500 MHz) spectroscopic data revealed the presence of eighteen hydrogens (Fig. 1a). The HREIMS data showing *m/z* values of 436.08, 458.06 and 474.03, corresponding to [M+H]⁺, [M+Na]⁺ and [M+K]⁺ respectively (Fig. 1b). 100% degree of purity is confirmed from RP-HPLC analysis with a retention time of 5.96 min (Fig. 1c).

Calibration curve and linearity :

Linear calibration graph is obtained for Rb ($n = 6$) in the concentration range 0.5–5 μg per band with high correlation coefficient ($r^2 > 0.99$). The mean value of slope and intercept are 3.1957 (± 0.05) and 327.699 (± 141.52), respectively. The detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ) limits obtained by the method are 150 and 450 ng respectively, which indicate the sensitivity of the method. A known concentration of Rb (2 μg) is spotted 16 times and the analyte concentration is experimentally determined from the peak area. The mean value is found to be 2.05 μg along with sd of 0.12 ($n = 16$). The reproducibility is found to be 97.37%.

Fig. 1. Spectroscopic analysis of isolated molecule : (a) ^1H NMR analysis, (b) HREIMS analysis, (c) HPLC analysis.

Chromatographic conditions :

In an attempt to optimize the mobile phase, toluene-ethyl acetate-methanol mixtures in different proportions are investigated. The use of toluene-ethyl acetate-methanol (2 : 1 : 1, v/v/v) resulted in sharp, well-defined peaks

(R_f value 0.53 ± 0.02). Well-defined bands are obtained only when the chamber is saturated with the mobile phase vapor for 30 min at room temperature before plate development. The optimum wavelength for detection and quantification used is 284 nm.

Stability and forced degradation studies :

There is no significant change in peak area and peak shape found for a sample solution after storage at room temperature ($25 \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) for 7 h and after storage at $2-8 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 h.

In stress induced stability testing, initially HCl (1 mol/L) is used for refluxation at $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The peak shape and area of Rb are almost unaltered up to 12 h. Hence the strength of acid is increased and studies are performed in 5 mol/L of HCl with refluxation time of 8 h. It is found that around 10% of the drug is degraded in 8 h, forming a major degradation product at R_f 0.72 (Fig. 2). Second study is performed with NaOH (5 mol/L). It is found that around 15% of the drug is degraded after 8 h of refluxation and the major degradation product appeared at R_f 0.88 (Fig. 2).

Validation parameters :

Precision :

The results of the repeatability and intermediate precision experiments are shown in Table 1. The developed method is found to be precise as the RSD values for repeatability and intermediate precision studies are less than 2%, as recommended by the guidelines of the Inter-

Fig. 2. Densitogram of Rb with degraded products; (1) Rb ($R_f = 0.53$), (2) acid treated degradant ($R_f = 0.72$) and (3) alkali treated degradant ($R_f = 0.88$).

national Conference on Harmonization (ICH). The mean intra-day and inter-day, variation, as % RSD are 1.61 and 1.76 respectively.

Table 1. Validation profile

Precision ($n = 6$)

Quantity (μg)	Repeatability ($n = 6$)		Intermediate precision ($n = 6$)	
	Concn. \pm sd	RSD (%)	Concn. \pm sd	RSD (%)
1	1.006 ± 0.02	1.79	1.008 ± 0.02	1.98
2	2.021 ± 0.04	1.90	2.028 ± 0.03	1.57
3	2.967 ± 0.03	1.15	3.023 ± 0.05	1.75

Robustness ($n = 3$)

Parameter	RSD of peak area (%)	% Recovery
Mobile phase composition (T : EA : M) ^a		
2 : 1 : 1	1.72	99.62
1.9 : 1 : 1	1.68	99.92
2.1 : 1 : 1	0.94	100.29
2 : 0.9 : 1	1.42	100.45
2 : 1.1 : 1	1.67	100.00
2 : 1 : 0.9	0.63	99.28
2 : 1 : 1.1	1.64	99.53
Plate activation time (min)		
5	1.08	100.69
2	0.24	98.84
7	1.25	100.50

Table-1 (contd.)

Time from application to development (min)		
10	0.60	98.90
20	1.07	100.60
Time from development to scanning (min)		
10	0.60	99.16
20	1.70	99.91
Development distance (cm)		
6	0.60	99.72
8	1.70	99.91

^aT, toluene; EA, ethyl acetate; M, methanol

Recovery ($n = 6$)

Level of % of recovery	Amount taken ($\mu\text{g}/\text{band}$)	Amount added ($\mu\text{g}/\text{band}$)	Amount recover ($\mu\text{g}/\text{band}$)	Recovery (%)	RSD (%)
0	2	0	2.01	100.67	1.63
50	2	1	2.99	99.66	1.60
100	2	2	4.02	100.51	1.72
150	2	3	4.99	99.78	1.73

Robustness :

Robustness of the method is checked after deliberate alterations of the analytical parameters, showed that areas of peaks of interest remained unaffected by small changes of the operational parameters. The low values of % RSD along with appreciable recovery obtained after introduction of these variations are indicative of the robustness of the method (Table 1).

Accuracy :

The recovery is found in the range of 99.66–100.67%, with RSD values not more than 2%. The method is found to be accurate and precise, as indicated by recovery studies (Table 1) as recoveries are close to 100%.

Specificity :

The specificity of the method is confirmed by simultaneously analyzing the standard and the sample. The bands for Rb from pharmaceutical formulations are confirmed by comparing the R_f value as well as the overlaid UV spectra of the separated bands with those from the standard (Fig. 3). The peak purity of Rb is assessed by comparing the spectra acquired at the peak start (S), peak apex (M), and peak end (E) of a band. It is found that $r(S,M)$ and $r(M,E)$ are >0.999 . The peak purity indicated the method specificity, as there is no interference from any impurities in the separation and determination of the Rb peak.

Fig. 3. Overlain UV spectra of Rb standard and samples.

Analysis of tablet formulation :

The method is also evaluated by the assay of commercially available tablets containing Rb. The % of assay (mean \pm sd) is found to be 99.53 ± 1.10 .

Experimental

Reagents and chemicals :

HPLC grade acetonitrile, dichloromethane, toluene, ethyl acetate and methanol are used in this experiment. The solvents are purchased from Ranbaxy Fine Chemicals Limited (New Delhi, India). Rb tablets (Xarelto[®], 10 mg per tablet), manufactured by Bayer Schering Pharma

AG, Germany, are obtained from local sources. Silica gel 60 F₂₅₄ TLC plates (20 × 20 cm, E. Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) are used as stationary phase.

Isolation of Rb from tablets :

Triturated tablet samples are extracted at room temperature by soaking with acetonitrile (ACN), followed by ultrasonication for 5 min. The filtrate is evaporated by rotary evaporator (Eyela rotary evaporator, N-1000), purified by column chromatography with mixtures of dichloromethane/methanol and finally recrystallised from dichloromethane. The crystal purity is checked by melting point analysis followed by HPLC, UV, NMR and ESI-Mass spectroscopic studies.

Preparation of standard solution and calibration plots (linearity) :

Accurately weighed Rb standard (10 mg) is dissolved in ACN to get concentration of 1 mg/mL. Different volumes of the stock solution (0.5–5 µL, at 0.5 µL intervals) are applied to TLC plates to furnish 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2, 2.5, 3, 3.5, 4, 4.5 and 5 µg of Rb per band. The plate is developed and scanned under chromatographic conditions. The peak areas are recorded for Rb. A good linear relationship between response (peak area) and concentration is observed over the range 0.5–5 µg per band.

Chromatographic conditions :

A Camag HPTLC system containing Linomat V (Switzerland) semiautomatic sample applicator, Hamilton syringe (100 µL), TLC Scanner-3 with winCATS software version 1.4.2 and twin-trough chamber (20 × 10 cm) are used in the present study. The plates are prewashed by methanol and activated at 110 °C for 5 min prior to chromatography. The samples are spotted in the form of bands of 6 mm width on silica gel plate with a constant application rate of 0.1 mL/s. The developed mobile phase is consisted of toluene : ethyl acetate : methanol in the ratio of 2 : 1 : 1 (v/v/v). Linear ascending development is carried out in 20 cm × 10 cm twin trough glass chamber. The time optimized for chamber saturation and stationary phase equilibration with mobile phase vapor is 30 min. The development distance and time are 7 cm and 15 min, respectively. Subsequent to the development, TLC plates are dried in current of air. Densitometric scanning at 284 nm is performed in the reflectance absorbance mode. The slit dimension is kept at 5 mm × 0.45 mm, and 10 mm/

s scanning speed is employed. The monochromator bandwidth is set at 20 nm, each track is scanned thrice and baseline correction is used.

Solution stability :

Standard stock solution is stored at room temperature (25 ± 2 °C). An aliquot of 2 µg/spot is assessed to check the degree of decomposition after 7 h and 24 h of storage.

Forced degradation studies :

The parent drug stability test guideline issued by the ICH suggests that stress studies must be carried out at the time of development of any analytical methodology of API⁷. A stock solution containing 1 mg/mL of ACN is used for forced degradation to provide an indication of the stability-indicating property and specificity of the proposed method. Acid decomposition studies are performed by refluxing the 10 mL stock solution in 10 mL of HCl (5 mol/L) at 80 °C for 8 h. After 8 h, 10 mL of NaOH (5 mol/L) is added for neutralization and final volume is made up to 50 mL with ACN. Base decomposition studies are performed by refluxing the 10 mL stock solution in 10 mL of NaOH (5 mol/L) at 80 °C for 8 h, followed by 10 mL of HCl (5 mol/L) is added for neutralization of alkaline test solution and final volume is made up to 50 mL with ACN. The resultant solutions are applied on TLC plate in such a way that final concentration achieved is 2 µg per spot for both acid and base degradation products and the chromatograms are run as described in the HPTLC section. The average peak area of Rb after application of three replicates is taken for analysis.

Method validation :

This method is validated and carried out as per the ICH guidelines⁸. Precision of the method is verified by repeatability and intermediate precision studies. Repeatability studies are performed by analysis of three different concentrations (1, 2 and 3 µg/spot) of the drug in linearity range in hexuplicate on the same day. Intermediate precision of the method is checked by repeating studies on three different days.

As per ICH guidelines, reproducibility of sample application is assessed. A definite quantity of Rb (2 µg) is spotted in sixteen replicates on the same plate and peak areas are measured.

The detection limit (LOD) and quantification limit (LOQ) of analyte are estimated as per eqs. (1) and (2).

$$\text{LOD} = (3.3 \times \text{Standard deviation of the Y-intercept}) / \text{slope of calibration curve} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{LOQ} = (10 \times \text{Standard deviation of the Y-intercept}) / \text{slope of calibration curve} \quad (2)$$

Robustness of the method :

By introducing deliberate small changes in the mobile phase composition (0.1 mL for each component), the effects on the results are examined. Mobile phases having different composition of the mixture of toluene, ethyl acetate and methanol (1.9 : 1 : 1, 2.1 : 1 : 1, 2 : 0.9 : 1, 2 : 1.1 : 1, 2 : 1 : 0.9 and 2 : 1 : 1.1) are tried and chromatograms are run. The plates are prewashed by methanol and activated at 110 °C for 2, 5 and 7 min respectively, prior to chromatography. Time from spotting to chromatography and from chromatography to scanning is varied by ± 10 min. Development distance is altered from 7 cm to 6 cm and 8 cm. One factor at a time is changed to study the effect. Robustness of the method is carried out at the concentration level of 2 μg per spot, in triplicate.

Specificity :

The specificity of the method is ascertained by analyzing standard drug and sample. The spot for Rb in sample is confirmed by comparing the R_f and UV spectrum of the spot with that of standard. The peak purity of Rb is assessed by comparing the spectrum at three different levels, i.e. peak start (S), peak apex (M), and peak end (E) position of the spot.

Accuracy (% recovery) :

The accuracy of the method is determined by calculating recoveries of Rb by the standard addition method. Known amount of standards of Rb (0, 1, 2 and 3 μg per band) are spiked to a prequantified sample (2 μg per band) of tablet extracts ($n = 6$ for each) and the mixtures are analyzed again. The amounts of Rb are determined

by measuring the peak areas and by fitting those values into the regression equation of the calibration plot.

Analysis of tablet formulation :

Twenty tablets are weighed accurately and finely powdered. A quantity of powder equivalent to 10 mg of Rb is weighed and prepared the solution with ACN containing 1 mg/mL using ultrasonication for 5 min. The sample solution is filtered through Whatman filter paper No. 41 and 2 μL is applied to the plate along with a spot of standard solution (statistically distributed). Procedure is repeated three times for the analysis of sample. The plate is developed and scanned under the optimized conditions as described. Peak areas are recorded and the amount of Rb in the formulation is estimated by the use of calibration plots.

Conclusions

The developed HPTLC technique is specific, precise, robust, sensitive, and provided accuracy for Rb analysis, which can be used in quality control of tablet dosage form.

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